

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

Saeed Khan

PhD Scholar, Department of Educational Leadership & Management, Qurtuba University, Dera Ismail Khan

Email: saeed786333@gmail.com

Muhammad Ehsan

PhD Scholar, Faculty of Education, International Islamic University Islamabad

Email: ehsankgp@hotmail.com

Farman Ali Shah

PhD Scholar, IER GOMAL University, Dera Ismail Khan

Email: the.shah315@gmail.com

Received on: 02-10-2022

Accepted on: 06-11-2022

Abstract

This correlational study is to describe the levels of school climate and its relationship with students' academic achievement. The population of the study consisted of all students of Zarghoon Town, Quetta, Balochistan, Pakistan who were attending public high schools. In accordance with the L.R. Gay criterion, out of 1650, 328 students or 20% of the class was chosen as the sample. One sample t-test was used to determine how students felt about the school, and Pearson Correlation was used to determine how well students performed academically in relation to the school atmosphere. According to the study's findings, students believe that having a supportive school environment is crucial for their academic achievement. Additionally, there is a correlation between students' academic success and the climate of the school.

Keywords: School Climate, School Atmosphere, Academic Achievement, School Culture, School Environment.

Introduction

There are many different types of schools. Some schools have a welcome, supporting, and pleasant vibe, while others have an exclusive, unsupportive, and even unsafe vibe. School climate refers to the emotions and behaviors that the atmosphere of a school elicits. The majority of studies concur that school climate is a multifaceted construct with intellectual, social, and physical elements, despite the fact that it is challenging to give a succinct explanation (Loukas, 2007). All educators, institution leaders, instructors, parents, and other interested parties have been working to raise children' academic performance for more than ten years. All the interested parties place a lot of emphasis on practical components like

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

homework, writing, and reading, but they fail to acknowledge the critical importance of some other factors like school atmosphere, which have a significant impact on students' academic success. Regarding the other factors, one that has a long-term effect on students' overall results is the school's culture (Hoy & Sabo, 1998). Life experience demonstrates that groups exist in our society where people engage with one another, the group's environment, and these groups come together for specific goals. The goal could be for a variety of reasons. To obtain serenity, happiness, comfort, a sense of belonging, safety, and nourishment, family members must live together in close relationships at home. On the other hand, relationships between higher-level employees and lower-level employees as well as between lesser staff members might vary greatly in the life of an organization such as a bank, corporation, mill, or factory. These people want to succeed in their field, grow, and receive rewards in the form of money and high organizational worth. Comparisons between student success and school atmosphere can assist school principals in concentrating their efforts to raise student achievement (MacNeil, Prater, & Busch, 2009).

There is a very vital educational life that exists on every educational institution, just as the house and organization have a life. But the school environment and life are the most crucial of these institutions. The life of a school is reflected in its retreatment, care, supervision, and association (i.e., relationship) with its teachers, students, and academic community (teaching and learning). Regarding behavioral change, school atmosphere is not a stand-alone factor; rather, it has several facets. Numerous inventory of school climate and its sub-variables have been developed through research. However, according to the study, the following factors now have the greatest impact on how students perceive their school's atmosphere and how that view is related to their academic success:

1. Communal (Association/relationship/communication/community)
2. Care (Safe and orderly environment)
3. Academic (Teaching and learning)

Berkowitz, Moore, Astor, and Benbenishty (2017) contend that while a well-furnished building structure is vital, it is insufficient to raise educational standards in order to sustain economic growth in the face of global competition. As mentioned by Gray, Kruse, & Tarter, (2016) that the achievement of students is due to the reasonable healthy school climate which permits to prevail the good collegial trust relationship, good academic teaching and learning. It was believed that informal classroom instruction was at least as important in determining student learning as the school climate, which was defined by Wertheimer (1971) as the "aggregate of attitudes of members of the school institution toward each other, toward their joint efforts and objectives, and toward the constraints and opportunities they meet there." Thus, the above school atmosphere health index is a crucial factor in raising students' accomplishment levels (National School Climate Center, 2015). However, due to shifting institutional regulations as well as students' interpersonal interactions with their fellow students, teachers, and administrators, the school environment is vulnerable to change. According to academic research, a good school climate enhances students' cognitive and affective results, which include their values, personal development, and fulfilment (Rovai, Wighting, & Liu, 2005). Academic achievement among middle school and high school pupils is correlated with school atmosphere. It may be possible to give enhanced and developmentally appropriate suggestions for the delivery of teaching and school-based

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

interventions that encourage good school well-being and student performance by accurately recognizing the roles of key characteristics of school climate by grade level (Daily et al., 2019). Students' feelings, willingness to participate, enthusiasm to contribute, and perceptions of themselves and others are all impacted by the school climate. School atmosphere is important, and in order to fulfil our commitment to expanding the definition of inclusion and engagement, schools must represent the principles of respect, equality, dignity, honesty, and safety. It is difficult to integrate and ensure effective and fair and equal opportunities for students with and without cognitive disabilities to involve with one another and establish lifetime behaviors and actions necessary to be fruitful youth and adults if a school climate does not represent these characteristics. It is strongly advised that those involved in education in third-world countries confront the situation head-on by making sure that a positive and welcoming school climate is established in order to ensure a sustainable development (Adeogun & Olisaemeka, 2011).

Purpose Statement

In encouraging and instructing the children on the proper path, the school climate is very important. It has been noted that public sector schools do not provide a healthy and welcoming environment for the school's academic growth. The bulk of public sector schools, in particular, have a bad academic climate, which is being lamented by the stakeholders. Similarly, instead of improving the school climate, stakeholders in schools employ various strategies such as winter campuses, guess papers, and tuition in their quest to earn high grades, casting doubt on the significance of school climate. Also, it is important to note that this research study exposes the most pressing issue in Zarghoon Town, District Quetta, Pakistan, with regard to people's ignorance of the importance of school atmosphere. This study aims to determine how students' perceptions of school climate relate to their academic performance at the secondary level in Quetta City, specifically among male students who attend Government Secondary Schools in Zarghoon Town, Quetta city.

Explanation of the Terminology

1. **School Climate:** this term is defined as Care & safety measure in school; teaching and learning in school and relationship between students and with their teachers.
2. **Academic:** the teaching and learning which takes place in the school where teacher teach the best to their knowledge and students achieve to their capability the knowledge.
3. **Communal:** relationship between students and with their teachers for the purpose of getting knowledge in order to get academic achievements.
4. **Care & Safety:** when students feel safe inside and outside on their way to school physically, psychologically and emotionally; and teacher, other staff members and the students care most towards each other's.
5. **Secondary Level Schools:** this is defined the Government controlled High schools and the annual Board exam is conducted by BBISE.
6. **Positive school climate:** is defined where the school members have good communal relationship with peaceful and calm environment and the academic activity i.e. teaching and learning is at the peak.
7. **Negative school climate:** is defined where the school members have bad

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

relationship with hostile and noisy and with bad teaching and learning experience.

8. Zarghoon Town: Quetta city is divided in two Town i.e. Zarghoon Town and Chiltan Town and the present study is conducted in Zarghoon Town Secondary Level Schools.

Literature Review

"School climate" is defined by the National School Climate Center (NSCC) as "the quality and character of school life" (2014, para.3). It also claimed that the norms, beliefs, and expectations that promote students' feelings of social, emotional, and physical safety, foster healthy relationships, nurture attitudes, and work together to create a supportive school climate for successful academic accomplishment. School climate is the instinctive, practically tangible intelligence and the awareness of security assurance, warm, cool safe or unsafe and belonging to the school, but most of the scholars agree that the total whole of school climate i.e. school rules, proceedings, and physical environment; staff interactions with peers and students; opportunities for students involvement and headship, beliefs and views point students fetch to the school as of their household life and the community (Jacob, 2017).

Climate vs. Culture in a School Context

It is necessary to take a closer look at how particular facets of school culture affect student learning (. School climate has some distinction Hoy, & Kottkamp, (1991) from a "psychological" angle and school culture noticed from a humanoid position. The climate of the institution is considered as behavior, as long as the culture is perceived as encompassing the principals and standards of the school (Hoy 1990, Heck and Marcoulides 1996). The most significant thing a school leader can do is pay attention to culture, according to organizational theorists who have said this for a long time. According to educational theorists, the principals' influence on learning is mediated by the environment and culture of the school rather than having a direct impact (Hallinger and Heck 1998). Climate as viewed as the total ecological worth within school and in association and the prevailing culture enhanced the significance of that climate and those ceremonies, ethics, and norms are signs of cultures (Schein, 1985, 1996). Despite the fact the theories give very small difference, climate as shared opinion and culture as shared customs, as follows (Hoy and Feldman, 1999) that shared opinions can be measured but shared custom is very difficult to measure. In a nutshell, the literature portrayed the stance that the description of climate is somehow easy than culture due to its abstraction. The measurement of climate is easy for a researcher to understand that whether the school climate positively or negatively impacts the students' academic achievement.

References of Some Foreign School Climate Studies

1. The school climate has various aspects that impact student achievements, that climate may be positive or negative. The positive essence of school climate enhances students' academic as well as overall achievements that help students ethically, materially and educationally. Although, negative school climate prevail the opposite of positive ethical, material and educational behavior which reflect poor picture of students' academic performance, interaction among peers, teachers, and others staff members and the most important students' academic achievement would be weak in the presence of negative school climate (Okendo, Christopher, & Jenifer, 2014).

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

2. In his book (DeWitt, & Slade, 2014) stated that expertise, that specializes in, and functioning on school climate is not fair and only a “feel good” concern is not enough but also a need a good teaching method and enhancing and communicating the positive school and classroom climate signifies teaching and learning. This gives the promotion to think to change the mindset of teachers and students for the betterment of school climate. Developing a positive school climate becomes a virtuous cycle. The more we distribute ownership to those in the school community, the larger role they play and strengthens the bond of relationship between peers, teachers and others staff members for better students' academic achievements.
3. When school climate is positive, DeWitt, & Slade, (2014) “school connectedness is strong, a positive school climate is directly related to improved academic achievement at all levels of schooling.” Fein, (2002) reported that climates of care, admiration, and expressive backing reduce violence in schools and enhance strong relationship and connectedness so, it decreases bullying and other negative behavior that lost wealth, time and provides an opportunity to solve the problem of shy students.
4. Parisi, Ramsey et al., (2015) examined how perceptions of school climate are impacted over a longer period is defensible. In one other research Caldarella, Shatzer, Gray, Young, & Young, (2011) probed the impacts of “school-wide teaching of social skills, admiration notes from teachers to students, placement of school instructions, pre-emptive screening for students at risk for emotional and behavioral disorders, and referrals of at-risk students for targeted interventions”, the school under examination indicated statistically weighty developments in instructor scores of school climate, though the control school likely to be the same or poorer.
5. Students perception of school climate was conducted by Kwong, & Davis, (2015) confirmed that poor school provision negatively effects on student's outcomes and greater levels of school close observation negatively impact the positive effect.
6. Pollack in his book stated that linking by way of human relationship is an essential part and serious expressive adhesive in the company of students and teacher of a culture and climate of care and admiration (Fein, 2002). In a research of (Hoy and Tarter, 1997; Thapa, Cohen, Guffey, & Higgins-D'Alessandro, 2013) found that “positive school climates incline to have improved academic achievement; contrary to, schools with negative climates as a result of insecure or aggressive environments incline to have worse outcome”.
7. In a recent study conducted by Gase, Gomez, Kuo, Glenn, Inkelas, & Ponce, (2017) surveyed the associations between management and students assessment of school climate and robust links were established among student result and details of engagement and care.
8. Johnson, & Stevens, (2006) Studied the “teachers' views of school climate in fifty-nine elementary schools were found that school with poor socioeconomic status (SES), the impacts of school climate on students outcomes was weaker than it was for schools in better SES communities.”
9. Riekie, Aldridge, & Afari, (2017) examined in South Australian School “the associations between students' perceptions of the school climate and self-reports of well-being, resilience and moral identity” and the outcomes “statistically significant and positive association among school-climate aspects and each of the three outcome variables.”
10. Sulak, (2016) indicate conduct and stated that cultural/folkloric arrangement

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

possibly effect school outcome plus the location of the school and the nearby wrongdoing.

Some Pakistani Reference Studies about School Climate

1. Hijazi & Naqvi (2006) found that educated mother`s children achievement is higher than illiterate; young mother`s child performed better than the aged mother; regular students achieved higher than irregular; higher income student did not perform better. In research by Rafiq, Fatima, Sohail, Saleem, & Khan, (2013) investigate those impacts of parental contribution in academic accomplishment about their known youngster and this study took place in Allama Iqbal Town, Lahore city. The result shows that parental contribution has positively impacted student`s results.
2. Branson, Baig & Begum, (2015) conducted a study at District level in Pakistan and examine the school head personal ethics impacts on school outcomes and the result shows that making a proper school-inclusive restorative climate is impacted by two key aspects. First, the association between individual and school conducts and manners secondly regularity of association between the conduct, manner, and behavior of school head in the creation of positive school climate.
3. Shehzad & Naureen (2017) conducted a study in Quetta City and found that “teacher self-efficacy has a positive impact on the students’ academic achievement.”
4. Dahar, et al. (2011) evidenced “the positive connection between Prior School Environment (PSEn) on the academic achievement of a student at the secondary stage in Punjab (Pakistan).”
5. Salfi & Saeed, (2007) conducted a descriptive (survey type) “on a sample of 90 secondary school head teachers and 540 primary, elementary and high school teachers working in the Public Sector school boys of Punjab province. The results were considerably correlated with school size Small schools shown positive school culture and show improved result than average and big schools.”
6. Tayyaba, (2012), studied the primary data source for the 2006 National Assessment Survey (NAS) of class four kids in Public Sector schools in the four Provinces and in the four main courses. The findings demonstrate that countryside and downtown students had similar academic outcomes. In Balochistan province, rural students beat their downtown fellow in three out of the four proven courses. In Punjab and Sindh, downtown students accomplished expressively well in communal studies and language tests. The reason for tested score variation is due to schooling situations, students’ family, and teachers’ distinctive features. In students outcomes the teachers training play key role, however, assets and multi-grade coaching have small significant.
7. Ali & Siddiqui, (2016) examined the influence of learning to set on students` outcomes at the secondary level school of five districts of Punjab province. “The correlation is ($r = .725$) between the Learning Environment and students outcomes moreover, the variables “of Learning Environment i.e. group procedures; teacher behavior and curriculum have a positive correlation with the academic achievement of the students. Additionally, this research displayed that Learning Environment has a positive impact on students’ outcomes that was “measured by regression analysis i.e. Academic Achievements = $-13.726 + 76.786$ (Learning Environment)” and the result recommends that vigorous education setting help good academic achievement.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

8. Shehzad & Naureen (2017) conducted a study in Quetta City and found that “teacher self-efficacy has a positive impact on the students’ academic achievement.”

Summary of the Above Related Studies

It is revealed from the above review of related studies in relation to perceptions’ of school climate and its relationship with their academic achievement that there has been done research work abroad and very little research in Pakistan. All the major study’s findings show that the perceptions’ of student’s school climate make relationship with student academic achievement in or other ways. However, in Pakistan especially in Balochistan capital Quetta this very important aspect has been ignored and the student’s perceptions of school climate and its relationship with students’ academic achievement especially in Pakistan and in others countries leaves ample space to conduct a study. Thus, it appears reasonably suitable on the part of the researcher to find out the current students perception about their school climate, its variables relationship and into the complications of academic climate at secondary level schools of Quetta Zarghoon town in common and to deliver positive helpful methods to develop the current condition of academic climate at the secondary level, and to provide some suggestion to improve students’ academic achievement.

Methodology

The research technique for the current study is included, and it details how the research problem has been investigated. With the aid of the theoretical framework, the theoretical framework and the associated theory about school climate have been analyzed, and after that, the operationalization of the school climate and its sub-factors took place. The research design is then explained along with the research paradigm, type, and nature. Additionally, descriptions of the population, sample, data piloting, data collection, process, and apparatus have been provided. In this chapter, the researcher also discusses the validity and reliability issues.

Theoretical Framework and the Related Theory

Theoretical Framework for School Climate

Sekaran, (2003) stated that “the theoretical framework helps us to postulate or hypothesize and test certain relationships and thus to improve our understanding of the dynamics of the situation” (p.87). Freiberg, (1999) explained that school climate is a word used to know individuals’ observations about their school. In addition, it combines convictions, qualities, and states of mind of understudies, educators, directors, guardians, office staff, overseers, cafeteria specialists, business partners, group individuals, and other people who assume essential parts of the life of the school. The view of understudies, educationalists, guardians, and immediate group are key segments of making a climate where instructors can educate, students can acquire, guardians can show a dynamic part in the training of their youngsters, and excellence and better achievements can be accomplished (Freiberg, 1999).

The Bio-Ecological Theory

Bioecological system theory presents child development within the context of relationship

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

systems that comprise the child's environment. The present study will practice a bioecological angle to discover the level to which students' perceptions of school influence and make a relationship with their insights of students' academic achievement. The framework emphasizes the importance of understanding bidirectional influences between individuals' development and their surrounding environmental contexts (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006).

The bio ecological model which (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006) represents a transition from a focus on the environment to a focus on proximal processes (the developing processes of regular interaction concerning person and surroundings) as devices of development. Thus, characteristics of the person as dependent variables; that is, as measures of developmental outcomes. Far less often are such characteristics examined as precursors and producers of later development from the perspective of the bio ecological model, their effectiveness in the latter role derives from their capacity to influence the emergence and operation of the proximal process. (Bronfenbrenner, & Morris, 2006, p.801-10).

Kuhn, Siegler, Damon, & Lerner, (2003) hypothesized that "whenever human being are introduced over prolonged eras of time to a setting that provides progressive means and encourages involvement in the proximal process (interrelationship between milieu and person) to a degree not experienced in the other settings in their lives, then the person of proximal processes to realize genetic potentials for developmental competence will be greater for those living in more disadvantaged and disorganized environments" (p.819). Haynes et al, (1997) of the view to assessing the understanding of both group students and teachers to measure school climate.

The Bio-ecological Theory in Perception of Students about their School Climate

Bronfenbrenner's Bioecological Point of view assesses the communication amongst individual and natural factors by giving a model delineating the different systems which influence the perception of a person's advancement and learning (Moran, Carlson, & Tableman, 2012). Moran, Carlson, & Tableman, (2012) further stated that such system levels incorporate the person's quick surroundings including family, social gatherings, and school, the connection of these conditions, outer situations, for example, the parent's working environment, and bigger social settings, all joining to influence, so development is a foundation and the social collaborations made inside it. Bronfenbrenner's (1979) bio ecological conceptual framework proposes that social progress happens through the multi-layered, communal relations that a single human being has to someone else and with the neighboring climate. Given the background of the climate of the school, specific behaviors are formed by the school climate, where every youngster is surrounded. For instance, the arrangement and situation of the school Care regarding safety and orderly environment, the procedure of particular school process (e.g., care), and the social contacts between students and teachers (e.g., communal), and the learning and teaching (e.g., academic) all play a role in manipulating student improvement (Wang, & Degol, 2016). Because, students and teachers spend most of his time in the school, therefore, school context greatly influence the perception of students either in positive or negative depending on the school climate health viability.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

Fig 3.1: Students' Perception of School Climate and its relationship with their Academic Achievement.

School Climate & Its Sub-Factors Operationalization

An independent variable is defined by Sukaran, (2003) as one that influences the dependent variable either in a positive or negative way. In this research study, the independent variable is school climate in light of the perceptions of students and its relationship with the students' achievement.

School Climate

It is well-defined in terms of enhancing a climate of a school that is dynamic to raise academic and interpersonal relations for the progress of students and schools on the way to achieve good results. The school climate in this study is the student's perception that they are safe psychologically and physiologically and the students get academically conclusive study both theoretically and practically and they have very well the communal relationship between teacher's students and among them as well.

But if on the other hand, the school is not safe, the communal relationship is bad between teachers and students, academic activities are poor, and then the student's perception of their school will give a poor picture of the school climate and will portray low academic achievements.

While this study has developed its own measure of school climate and the following sub-factors of school climate independent variable sub-factors are operationally defined to conduct this study.

Communal (Relationship among teachers and Students)

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

A sub-factor of the independent variable that measures school climate is communal, which is also known as the quality of relationships (Trust, interpersonal relationships between teachers and students, affiliation). The second degree of connectivity (cohesion, sense of belonging, student activities). The third preference is for variety, cultural knowledge, justice, and self-determination. The social environment of the school, which refers to the ways in which relationships occur between students and staff, demonstrates the strength, ties of relationships, and degree of freedom. Thus, as long as the community keeps its good promises, student academic achievement will rise (Jia et al., 2009).

Care & Safety

The sub-factors of care are: social/emotional (absence of coercion guidance), rule and regulation & control, (confrontation resolution, transparency, equality, and regularity of precedent, trust in school regulation, physical condensed disturbance, and offense), sense of security, (safety measure: safety tool and sensors, protectors), and physical condensed disturbance and offense (Wang, & Degol, 2016). School care is the concrete, emotional, legal, and statutory framework that provides a sense of safety in the classroom (Devine and Cohen 2007; Morrison et al. 1994; Wilson 2004).

Academic (Teaching and Learning)

The academic sub-factors include teaching and learning (quality of instruction, assessment of learners, the eagerness of school staff, pupil motivation, expectations of school staff, achievement of goals, adoption of supportive practices by instructors), professional development (review and evaluation of educational practices, favorable conditions for advancement through professional development), and other factors (Wang, & Degol, 2016). The academic mandate of the school atmosphere, which includes administration, instruction, and education, is a tool for enhancing teaching and learning (Thapa et al. 2013).

Students' Academic Achievement

The student's performance on the most recent Secondary Board test is shown here. As a result, the outcome influences the students' progress over the entire year. Thus, the current study's dependent variable is the percentage of grades students received in their secondary school's Balochistan Board of Intermediate & Secondary Education Quetta annual exam results, which were released in March 2018.

Design of the Study

Type of Research

The research methodology of this study is quantitative, and descriptive statistics are performed using quantitative statistical methods. The percentage of the pass and fail students was included in the researcher's description of the study's demographics. In Zarghoon town, Quetta city public secondary level schools, a survey was created using quantitative research to determine the relationship between school climate and students' academic progress. Additionally, a correlation coefficient and a single sample t-test were utilized in this study to establish how significant students believed their school climate to be.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

Population

The study's population consisted of all 1640 students from the 19 Government Male High Schools in Baluchistan who took the Class 9 exam in the most recent BBISE exam, which was held in March 2018.

Sample of the Study

The Sample is a representation of the whole population. The sample has all the features of the total population. All nineteen male Government High Schools in Zarghoon Town, Quetta have been chosen through L.R Gay rules, 20%, wherein, each school 10th class attendance register was used for drawing a simple random sample for administrating the survey. .

Table 3.1.: Distribution of Population and Samples of the study

	Population	Sample
Number of Schools	19	
Number of Students	1640	328

3.7 Instrumentation (data collection tools)

Neuman, (2014) in his book wrote that “quantitative data often use experiments, surveys, and statistics, so, for the present study the researcher used Likert scale, Students School Climate Survey Questionnaire (SSCSQ). School climate, student's perception data were administered by the execution of a 36-itemstoolscomposed for analyzing the problems in this study. The school climate survey was planned to attain a true perception of the Secondary Schools of Zarghoon Town Quetta city. The school climate survey guided by the review of literature wherein, the school climate sub factors communal, academic and care & safety measures were incorporated in the survey instruments. The survey included 36 items with a five-point, Likert-type scale i.e. 1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-neutral, 4-agree, 5-strongly agree. Plus, the survey questions 1 to 14 are academic (teaching & learning), 15 to 24 are about School Care & Safety measure and 25 to 36 are about Communal (relationship between students and with their teachers) are the survey items for overall school climate.

The surveys instruments were evaluated by a group of 4 specialists who are specialized in the field of education were nominated for validity and reliability. There were only few minor suggestions were made related the wording and to include one items and exclude some items which were made to the survey instruments. The students' academic achievements were assessed through their 9th-grade annual BBISE, exam held in March 2018.

4.3 Hypotheses of the Study

Null-Hypothesis

H0 1: Students in secondary schools in the Zarghoon, Town Quetta do not see the school climate as an important factor that will influence their success in school.

H0 2: Secondary school students in Zarghoon, Town of Quetta, believe that their marks on the BBISE exam won't improve despite the reasonable school climates.

Alternative Hypothesis

H₀ 1: Students in secondary schools in Zarghoon Town Quetta see the school climate as an important factor that will influence their success in school.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

H₁ 2: Secondary school students in Zarghoon, Town of Quetta, believe that the friendly educational environments will improve their scores on the BBISE exam.

4.6 Demographic Analysis

The demographic variables for the entire 29 Zarghoon Town, Quetta City Secondary Schools are indicated below.

Table 4.1 Students of Class 10th Age frequency and percentage distribution.

Ages Range of Students	Frequency	Percent
14-16 years	152	46
17-19 years	164	50
20 & Above yrs.	12	04
Total	328	

As the above Table 4.1 portrays the students age for 14-16 years old are 46%, students age for 17-19 years old are 50% and 20 & above is only 4%. It shows that student age 14 to 19 constituted 96 % of the total population.

Table 4.2 Students of class 10th language wise distribution of Zarghoon Town Quetta.

Languages	Frequency	Percent
Pashto	240	74
Persian	22	7
Urdu	29	9
Others	37	12
Total	328	100

The students' ethnicity Table 4.2 shows the ethnicity distribution for the Zarghoon Town Secondary Schools where 73% of are Pashto speaking, 7 % are Persian, 9% are Urdu and 12% respectively. This means that most of the students who participated in the study belong to Pashtun community.

4.7 Descriptive Statistics

The following Table 4.3 shows the pass/fail status distribution of the 328 sampled students.

Table 4.3 9th Grade Annual Exam Frequency and Percentage status in BBISE-2018

Status	Frequency	Percent
Fail	72	22
Pass	256	78
Total	328	100

The researcher has chosen the academic achievements of the students as variable to test the relationship with school climate. The data shows that 78 % pass and 22 % fail students were randomly selected for the study.

4.8 Statistics were tested

The research questions and hypotheses were framed and tested using SPSS 22 software. The following tests were carried out:

- Reliability test & Cronbach's Alpha determination,
- Outlier check for the academic achievement scores

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

- One sample t-test
- A Pearson correlation

4.9 Consistency and reliability Testing

Cronbach's Alpha is calculated as a quantity of inner cohesion between Questionnaires. This Cronbach's Alpha is from zero to one, and when the alpha is near to 1 the inner consistency is stronger between SCSSQ questionnaires.

Table 4.4 Reliability Statistics, SCSSQ 1-36 Questionnaires.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.850	36

Table 4.5. Mean, Variance, Std. Deviation and number of school, SCSSQ 1-36 Questionnaire

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
136.66	373.624	19.329	36

A Cronbach's alpha analysis was conducted on the School Climate Students Survey Questionnaire from SCSSQ01 to SCSSQ36. Moreover, the above table 4.4 shows alpha level .850 which indicates that the scale had an adequate level of inter-item reliability and consistency.

4.10 Outlier, to check for the academic achievement scores

Figure 4.1 Boxplot, 10th Grade Students Overall Achievements in 9th Grade Annual Exam.

The above table 4.1 shows that the students' academic achievements score which they got in their annual Baluchistan Board of Intermediate & Secondary Education (BBISE), 9th grade exam result held in March 2018, has no outlier and the researcher is able to run the t-test and Pearson correlation tests on the data.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

4.11 The perception of students about school climate

The researcher aims to know how the students feel about their school climate. The researcher used 5-point Likert scale: -

1. Strongly agree 2. Agree 3. Neutral 4. Disagree 5. Strongly Disagree

Also, the researcher tests the response of the students against " $\mu = 3$ " (Neutral), and $\alpha = .05$. Moreover, to know students' perception, the researcher runs one sample t-test. The population means was assumed " $\mu = 3$ " and the results on either side will show the students perception, that is, whether their perceptions are statistically significant or not. Moreover, the researcher has tested the school climate sub-factors i.e. (Academic, care & safety and Communal) separately. Also, the researcher had tested the first hypothesis sub-factor Academic (Teaching & Learning) with one sample t-test is as under:-

4.11.1 The Perception of students about Academic (Teaching & Learning).

(i). H_0 : the students' in high school in the Zarghoon Town Quetta are indifferent in their view about their school academic (teaching & learning) environment, that is,
 $\mu = 3$

(ii). H_1 : the students' in high school in the Zarghoon Town Quetta are different in their view about their school academic (teaching & learning) environment, that is,
 $\mu \neq 3$

Table 4.6 One-Sample Statistics, student's perception about school academic (teaching & learning)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Academic	328	3.82	.630	.035

Table 4.7 One-Sample t-test, Students Perception about Academic (Teaching & Learning)

Test Value = 3						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Academic	23.432	327	.000	.815	.75	.88

Reject the null hypothesis & accept the alternative Hypothesis, the Students who were surveyed had a significantly favorable perception about their school academic (teaching & learning) Table 4.6 & 4.7 result indicate, $t(327) = 23.43$, $p = .000$, which means students are of the view to have good teaching and learning.

4.11.2 Perception of students about their School Care & Safety.

(i). H_0 : The students' in high school in Zarghoon Town Quetta are indifferent in their view about their school Care & Safety measure, that is,
 $\mu = 3$

(ii). H_1 : The students' in high school in Zarghoon Town Quetta are different in their view about their school Care & Safety measure, that is,
 $\mu \neq 3$

Table 4.8 One sample statistics, student's perception about school Care & Safety.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Care & Safety	328	3.40	.623	.034

Table 4.9 One sample t-test, student's perception about Care & Safety

Test Value = 3						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	(2-Mean Difference)	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Care & Safety	11.646	327	.000	.401	.33	.47

Reject the null hypothesis & accept the alternative Hypothesis, the Students who were surveyed had a significantly favorable perception about their school Care & Safety measure, Table 4.8 & 4.9 result indicate, $t(327) = 11.646$, $p = .000$, which means students are of the view to have complete Care & Safety measure in their School.

4.11.3 Perception of students about Communal (Relationship between the students and with their teachers).

(i). H_0 : The students' in high school in the Zarghoon Town Quetta are in different in their view about school Communal (Relationship), that is,

$$\mu = 3$$

(ii). H_1 : The students' in high school in the Zarghoon Town Quetta are different in their view about school Communal (Relationship), that is,

$$\mu \neq 3$$

Table 4.10 one sample statistics, student's perception about school Communal (Relationship).

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Communal (Relation)	328	3.55	.568	.031

Table 4.11 One Sample statistic, student's perception of overall Communal (Relationship).

Test Value = 3						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	(2-Mean Difference)	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Communal (relation)	17.584	327	.000	.552	.49	.66

Reject the null hypothesis & accept the alternative Hypothesis, the Students who were surveyed had a significantly favorable perception about their school Communal (Relationship between students and with their teachers) Table 4.10 & 4.11 result indicate, $t(327) = 17.584$, $p = .000$, which means students prefer positive (Relationship between the students and with their teachers).

4.12 Perception of students about overall School Climate.

As the researcher tested the three sub factors of school climate i.e. Academic, Care & Safety and Communal, and the students prefer significant on the three sub-factors of school climate

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

and now it is tested for the overall school climate when $\mu = 3$ and $\alpha = .05$.

H₀: The students' in high school in the Zarghoon Town Quetta are indifferent in their view about their school climate, that is,

$\mu = 3$

H₁: The students' in high school in the Zarghoon Town Quetta are different in their view about their school climate, that is,

$\mu \neq 3$

Table 4.12 one sample statistics, student's perception about their overall school climate

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Overall School Climate	328	3.61	.490	.0270

Table 4.13 One sample t-test, student's perception about overall School Climate

Test Value = 3						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	(2-Mean Difference)	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Overall school climate	22.614	327	.000	.612	.559	.666

Note. Questions 33, 29, 23, 21, 20, revers coded method were employed.

Reject the null hypothesis & accept the alternative Hypothesis, the Students who were surveyed had a significantly favorable perception about their school overall School Climate Table 4.12 & 4.13 result concluded, $t(327) = 22.614$, $p = .000$, which means students perceptions are of significant nature and they see the school climate an important factor that will influence their academic achievements.

4.13 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis measures the strength and relationship of association between two variables. Therefore, the Pearson Correlation and scatter plot were computed to tests the relationship. The appended table reports a comprehensive correlation analysis with the dependent variables students' academic achievements and the independent variable school climate three sub-factors i.e. "Academic (Teaching & Learning)", "Care & Safety", and "Communal (Relationship between students and with their teachers)". Similarly, Positive, healthy and conductive school climate is the key factor to have good academic achievement and it will also positively influence the perception of students.

4.14 The Pearson Correlation

A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was computed to measure the relationship between the School Climate sub-factors i.e. "Academic (Teaching & Learning)", "Care & Safety", and "Communal (Relationship between students and with their teachers)" and Students Academic Achievements." Therefore, the Hypothesis No. 2 is tested, that is:-

Null-Hypothesis

H₀ 2: For students in high schools in the Zarghoon, Town Quetta feel that the reasonable school climates will not higher their grades in the BBISE exam.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

Alternative Hypothesis

H₁ 2: For students in high schools in the Zarghoon, Town Quetta feel that the reasonable school climates will higher their grades in the BBISE exam.

Table 4.14 Pearson Correlation between academic achievement and the three school climate variable i.e. Academic, Care & Safety and communal (Relationship)

		1	2	3	4
1.Academic Achievement	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N				
2.Academic (Teaching & Learning)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.268**			
3.Care & Safety	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.085	.412**		
4.Communal (Relationship within students and with the teacher)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.167**	.580**	.393**	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.15 Students over all perception relationship with their academic achievements. Correlations

		1	2
1.Academic Achievements	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1	
2.Students about School Climate Perception	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.228**	328

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

Figure 4.2 Students' Academic Achievement and School Climate

"A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was computed to assess the relationship between the School Climate sub-factors i.e. "Academic (Teaching & Learning)", "Care & Safety", and "Communal (Relationship between students and with their teachers)" and Students Academic Achievements. There was a positive correlation between the School Climate sub-factors "Academic (Teaching & learning) between students' academic achievement, Table 4.12 result indicate, $r = 0.268$, $n = 328$, $p = 0.000$, competent and good teaching & learning is the key factors of students achievements. And a positive correlation between the school climate sub-factor Communal (Relationship between students and with their teachers). However, there is no correlation between School Climate sub-factor Care & Safety between students' academic achievements, Table 4.12 result indicate, $r = 0.085$, $n = 328$, $p = 0.126$.

Moreover, the result of the Pearson correlation between the overall school climate and students' academic achievement, 4.12, $r = 0.167$, $n = 328$, $p = 0.002$, which means that there is a more strong positive bond between school teachers and students and among students is the sign of high academic achievement.

Similarly, the Table 4.13, shows the Positive correlation between overall school climate and students' academic achievement, Table 4.12 result indicate, $r = 0.228$, $n = 328$, $p = 0.000$. A scatterplot summarizes the results (Figure 4.2) Overall, there is a weak positive correlation between school climate and students' academic achievements. Therefore, **Reject the null**

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

hypothesis & accept the alternative Hypothesis, which means providing an enhanced positive, improved, and reasonable School Climate, is correlated with higher Academic Achievement.

Discussion

The current study's objective is to evaluate the connection between classroom culture and students' academic success in the BBISE-2018 exam in Zarghoon Town, Quetta. Mitchell, Bradshaw, and Leaf (2010) found that classroom-level factors were more closely associated with teachers' perceptions of climate, whereas school-level factors were more closely associated with students' perceptions. As a result, the students' perceptions were evaluated for the significance of school climate, including whether it has a relationship to academic achievement. As to whether this will support the relationship between school climate and students' academic achievements and whether it would be a practical alternative to improve students' academic achievements, it is important to understand the relationship between school climate and students' academic achievements.

Assessing the research question No.1 considering the perception of student's significance nature about their school climate, quantitative designed one sample t-test was computed to understand the perception of the Secondary level schools of the Zarghoon Town, Quetta city a total of 19 schools, 328 students were involved in the survey with 97% return rate. The results from the one sample t-tests show that the perceptions of students are of significant nature about their school climate. These findings are noteworthy since the student's population is aware of the good, positive and improved school climate and they think that improved school climate means higher academic achievements, which is also validated the study of (Murray, Hollis, Cross, & Davis, 2007).

The current study measures the perception of school climate in relation to students' academic achievement through School Climate Students Survey Questionnaires with 5 points Likert scale in Public Secondary Schools of Zarghoon Town, Quetta city. The researcher used the Pearson correlation on school climate and also assesses the relationship with school climate sub-factors exclusively for Academic, Care & Safety and Communal. Henceforward, the outcomes of the Academic (teaching & learning) relationship is positive with academic achievements, which gives the logic of good academic (teaching & learning) increase students' academic achievements (Gray, Kruse, & Tarter, (2016) concluded that "enabling school structures, collegial trust, and academic emphasis simultaneously contributed to the explanation of Professional Learning Communities, PLCs".

However, the care & safety does not make any relationship with academic achievements may be whatever the reason of the bad and deteriorating situation of safety in Quetta City and the students may be used to the situation of law & order which is not good from the last 17 years. Moreover, Barnes, Brynard, & De Wet, (2012), study conducted in South Africa, Eastern Cape through the results indicates that "school culture and school climate can be used to explain a significant percentage of variance in school violence" whereas, "the f^2 values indicate that, with the exception of two aspects of the variance physical and verbal harassment, the results did not have any practical value" and one other study by Bosworth, Ford, & Hernandez, (2011) in Arizona School concluded that 11 out of 9 schools staff and students did not express devastating fears about safety. In addition, almost all studies support that safe school

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

contribute to the academic achievements of students. Moreover, the results of the first hypothesis are also in favor that safety is significant which are in favor of school climate care & safety.

School climate gives us the understanding of a fit and vigorous school climate where according to Voight & Nation (2016) the students are calm, happy, dedicated, and have a good communal relationship between students and with their teachers; the teachers have the capacity to transfer the learning at the students level, the students should give voice, the students should feel safe. The school climate got more attention in the recent past and educators are making approaches to improve academic achievement (Voight & Nation, 2016). In a school wherever the school climate is commendably managed and given prominence the signal of students' negative perception is decreased and students' positive perception is increased which will eventually escalate students' academic achievements (Ruiz, McMahon, & Jason, 2018).

Conclusion

The intention of this correlational research study is to look at the relationship, between school climate and students' academic achievements, from the perspective of students of Zarghoon Town Secondary level Schools. It is very supportive to know the relationship between school climate and student's academic achievement and this will be a workable strategy for the administration of educational authorities and heads of educational institutions to progress towards positive school climate to take measurable step to ensure it for students. Still, healthy and conclusive school climate encourages healthy educational activity in school for all the educators and this must be the future target achieved by all the educational administration stakeholders.

Future Recommendation

The findings of this research study provide a basis for upcoming studies and methods to fully know about the possible benefit of school climate in future studies designed. For taking more significance of the study future researchers should use the linear regression analysis to find out the cause and effect of the school climate on students' academic achievement. Besides, the Ministry of Education with the help of non-governmental organizations may launch a campaign of awareness and bring to the front the significance of school climate influence on students' academic achievements. Also, this study may be conducted by surveying both the genders of teachers and students i.e. males and females. To obtain significant result the researcher should go for an appropriate sample size rather than small sample size.

References

1. Adeogun, A. A., & Olisaemeka, B. U. (2011). Influence of School Climate on Students' Achievement and Teachers' Productivity for Sustainable Development. *Online Submission*, 8(4), 552-557.
2. Ali, Z., & Siddiqui, M. U. R. (2016). School Climate: Learning Environment as a Predictor of Student's Academic Achievement. *Journal of Research & Reflections in Education (JRRE)*, 10(1).
3. Barnes, K., Brynard, S., & De Wet, C. (2012). The influence of school culture and school climate on violence in schools of the Eastern Cape Province. *South African Journal of Education*, 32(1), 69-82.
4. Bosworth, K., Ford, L., & Hernandez, D. (2011). School climate factors contributing to student and faculty perceptions of safety in select Arizona schools. *Journal of school health*, 81(4), 194-201.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

5. Branson, C. M., Baig, S., & Begum, A. (2015). Personal values of principals and their manifestation in student behavior: A district-level study in Pakistan. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 43(1), 107-128.
6. Bronfenbrenner, Urie (1979). *The ecology of human development: experiments by nature and design*. Boston: Harvard University Press.
7. Bronfenbrenner, U., & Morris, P. A. (2006). The bioecological model of human development. *Handbook of Child Psychology*, 568-586.
8. Caldarella, P., Shatzer, R. H., Gray, K. M., Young, K. R., & Young, E. L. (2011). The effects of school-wide positive behavior support on middle school climate and student outcomes. *RMLE Online*, 35(4), 1-14.
9. Dahar, M. A., Dahar, R. A., Dahar, R. T., & Faize, F. A. (2011). Impact of teacher quality on the academic achievement of students at a secondary stage in Punjab (Pakistan). *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 19(1), 97-105.
10. Daily, S. M., Mann, M. J., Kristjansson, A. L., Smith, M. L., & Zullig, K. J. (2019). School climate and academic achievement in middle and high school students. *Journal of School Health*, 89(3), 173-180.
11. Devine, J. F., & Cohen, J. (2007). *Making your school safe: strategies to protect children and promote learning*. Columbia University, NY: Teachers College Press. Every Student Succeeds Act of 2015, 20 U.S.C. & 6301 et seq. (2015).
12. DeWitt, P., & Slade, S. (2014). *School Climate Change: How Do I Build a Positive Environment for Learning?* (ASCD Arias). ASCD.
13. Fein, R. A. (2002). Threat assessment in schools: A guide to managing threatening situations and to creating safe school climates. DIANE Publishing. Page-1-22 Retrieved online <https://books.google.com.pk/books>
14. Gase, L. N., Gomez, L. M., Kuo, T., Glenn, B. A., Inkelas, M., & Ponce, N. A. (2017). Relationships among student, staff, and administrative measures of school climate and student health and academic outcomes. *Journal of School Health*, 87(5), 319-328.
15. Gray, J., Kruse, S., & Tarter, C. J. (2016). Enabling school structures, collegial trust and academic emphasis: Antecedents of professional learning communities. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 44(6), 875-891.
16. Hallinger, P., & Heck, R. H. (1998). Exploring the principal's contribution to school effectiveness: 1980-1995. *School effectiveness and school improvement*, 9(2), 157-191.
17. Haynes, N. M., Emmons, C., & Ben-Avie, M. (1997). School climate as a factor in student adjustment and achievement. *Journal of educational and psychological consultation*, 8(3), 321-329.
18. Heck, and Marcoulides, (1996) School culture and performance: testing the in variance of an organizational model. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 7(1), 76-96.
19. Hijazi, S. T., & Naqvi, S. M. M. (2006). A study of the factors affecting students' achievement in Pakistan. *Bangladesh E-Journal of Sociology*, 3(1), 70-81.
20. Hoy, W. K. (1990) Organizational climate and culture: a conceptual analysis of the school workplace. *Journal of Educational and Psychological Consultation*, 1(2), 149-168.
21. Hoy, W. K., Tarter, C. J., & Kottkamp, R. B. (1991). *Open schools, healthy schools: Measuring organizational climate*. Corwin Press.
22. Hoy, W. K., and Tarter, C.J. (1997). *The Road to Open and Healthy School. A Handbook for change, Elementary and Middle School Edition* (Thousand Oaks,CA: Orwin).
23. Hoy, W. K., & Sabo, D. J. (1998). *Quality middle schools: Open and healthy*. Corwin Press, Inc., 2455 Teller Road, Thousand Oaks, CA 91320-2218 (paperback: ISBN-0-8039-6421-8, \$24.95; cloth: ISBN-0-8039-6420-X, \$55.95).
24. Hoy, W. K., & Feldman, J. A. (1999). Organizational health profiles for high schools. *School climate: Measuring, improving and sustaining healthy learning environments*, 85.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

25. Jacob, M. (2017). Improving the Social-Emotional Climate of our nation's schools through the Whole School Climate Framework.
26. Jia, Y., Way, N., Ling, G., Yoshikawa, H., Chen, X., Hughes, D., & Lu, Z. (2009). The influence of student perceptions of school climate on socio emotional and academic adjustment: A comparison of Chinese and American adolescents. *Child Development*, 80(5), 1514-1530.
27. Johnson, B., & Stevens, J. J. (2006). Student achievement and elementary teachers' perceptions of school climate. *Learning Environments Research*, 9(2), 111-122.
28. Kuhn, D., Siegler, R., Damon, W., & Lerner, R. M. (2003). Handbook of child psychology. Handbook of child psychology.
29. Kwong, D., & Davis, J. R. (2015). School Climate for Academic Success: A Multilevel Analysis of School Climate and Student Outcomes. *Journal of Research in Education*, 25(2), 68-81.
30. Loukas, A. (2007). What is school climate, *Leadership compass*, 5(1), 1-3.
31. MacNeil, A. J., Prater, D. L., & Busch, S. (2009). The effects of school culture and climate on student achievement. *International Journal of leadership in Education*, 12(1), 73-84.
32. Mitchell, M. M., Bradshaw, C. P., & Leaf, P. J. (2010). Student and teacher perceptions of school climate: A multilevel exploration of patterns of discrepancy. *Journal of School Health*, 80(6), 271-279.
33. Moran, E., Carlson, J. S., & Tableman, B. (2012). School Climate and Learning. In *Encyclopedia of the Sciences of Learning* (pp. 2962-2966). Springer US.
34. Morrison, G. M., Furlong, M. M. J., & Morrison, R. L. (1994). School violence to school safety: reframing the issue for school psychologists. *School Psychology Review*, 23, 236- 256.
35. Murray, N. G., Low, B. J., Hollis, C., Cross, A. W., & Davis, S. M. (2007). Coordinated school health programs and academic achievement: a systematic review of the literature. *Journal of school health*, 77(9), 589-600.
36. National School Climate Center. (2014). School Climate. Retrieved from <http://www.schoolclimate.org/climate/>
37. National School Climate Center. (2015). FAQs for the CSCI. Retrieved from <http://www.schoolclimate.org/climate/documents/faqs-csci-September-2017.pdf>.
38. Okendo, E., Christopher, N., & Jenifer, M. (2014). Relationships between school climate and students' academic achievement in ksce examinations: a case of kisii county-kenya [abstract]. *European-American Journal*, 1(2), 1-17.
39. Parisi, J. M., Ramsey, C. M., Carlson, M. C., Xue, Q. L., Huang, J., Romani, W. A., & Tan, E. J. (2015). Impact of Experience Corps participation on school climate. *Prevention Science*, 16(5), 744-753.
40. Rafiq, H. M. W., Fatima, T., Sohail, M. M., Saleem, M., & Khan, M. A. (2013). Parental involvement and academic achievement: A study on secondary school students of Lahore, Pakistan. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(8), 209-223.
41. Riekke, H., Aldridge, J. M., & Afari, E. (2017). The role of the school climate in high school students' mental health and identity formation: A South Australian study. *British Educational Research Journal*, 43(1), 95-123.
42. Rovai, A. P., Wighting, M. J., & Liu, J. (2005). School climate. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 6(4).
43. Ruiz, L. D., McMahon, S. D., & Jason, L. A. (2018). The Role of Neighborhood Context and School Climate in School-Level Academic Achievement. *American journal of community psychology*.
44. Salfi, N. A., & Saeed, M. (2007). Relationship between school size, school culture and students' achievement at the secondary level in Pakistan. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 21(7), 606-620. Retrieved from <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/abs/10.1108/09513540710822201>
45. Schein, E. H. (1985). *Organizational Culture and Leadership*. San Francisco: Josey-Bass. Google Scholar.

School Climate and its Relationship with Students' Academic Achievement

46. Schein, E. H. (1996). Culture: The missing concept in organization studies. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 229-240.'
47. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2003). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-building Approach*. USA: John Willey & Sons.
48. Shahzad, K., & Naureen, S. (2017). Impact of Teacher Self-Efficacy on Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 4(1), 48-72.
49. Sulak, T. N. (2016). School climate and academic achievement in suburban schools. *Education and Urban Society*, 48(7), 672-684.
50. Tayyaba, S. (2012). Rural-urban gaps in academic achievement, schooling conditions, student, and teachers' characteristics in Pakistan. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 26(1), 6-26.
51. Thapa, A., Cohen, J., Guffey, S., & Higgins-D'Alessandro, A. (2013). A review of school climate research. *Review of educational research*, 83(3), 357-385.
52. Voight, A., & Nation, M. (2016). Practices for improving secondary school climate: A systematic review of the research literature. *American journal of community psychology*, 58(1-2), 174-191.
53. Wang, M.T., & Degol, J. L. (2016). School climate: A review of the construct, measurement, and impact on student outcomes. *Educational Psychology Review*, 28(2), 315-352.
54. Wertheimer, P. A. (1971). School climate and student learning. *The Phi Delta Kappan*, 52(9), 527-530.
55. Wilson, D. (2004). The interface of school climate and school connectedness and relationships with aggression and victimization. *Journal of School Health*, 74, 293- 299.